

THE SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC IMPACT OF THE RUSSIA-UKRAINE WAR IN ALBANIA (IN FOCUS THE IMPACT OF THE CONSUMPTION OF SOME BASIC BASKET PRODUCTS)

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ABSTRACT

The start of the Russia-Ukraine war on February 24, 2022, immediately affected the economy of all countries, such as European countries and worldwide. Our country, as a developing country, immediately felt the impact of this war. Still faced with the consequences caused by the "Covid 19" pandemic, now for our country but also the whole world must face the effects and consequences of the Russia-Ukraine war. Thus, the markets immediately reflected price increases for all domestic and imported products, reaching an inflation level of 8% in August 2022, according to data declared by the Bank of Albania and INSTAT. High and Unforeseen Inflation in our country, considering that our country is a developing country, significantly affected the behavior of consumers in the market. The market reflected an immediate decline in consumption. Mainly, this decrease was immediately reflected in the basic products of the basket because inflation caused a decrease in purchasing power since we do not have a wage indexation to deal with the effects caused by inflation. In this, a study on changes in the consumption of some products with income based on prices, taking into account all their households and changes in power. The study reflects the consumer's diet towards basic basket products such as food, fruits and vegetables, oil, etc. This paper will reflect the declines in consumption for basic basket products as a result of inflation caused mainly by the war, which directly affected the decrease in consumer welfare. The recommendation of some possible solutions to the situation through government intervention will be reflected during this study.

Keywords: inflation, economic and social impact, product basket, consumers, market, government intervention.

Economic-statistical analysis of the impact of the Russia-Ukraine war on the consumption of some basic basket products

During the year 2022, the whole world felt the consequences of the Russia-Ukraine war, a war which still continues. It has deepened the negative consequences in the economy of many countries, consequences which are deepening. The negative impact caused by this war has been felt especially for developing countries such as Albania.

While our country had not yet recovered from the economic crisis caused by the global pandemic "Covid 19", it was found unprepared to face a very high inflation, inflation which reached about 8.3% in October 2022. The increase in inflation caused a chaos in our economy.

As a result, the confrontation between the West and Russia has greatly escalated, which will have a long-term, large-scale negative impact on most European companies and economies. (*Russia's War in Ukraine: Consequences for European Countries' Businesses and Economies Anatolijs Prohorovs*)

The Consumer Price Index in June 2022 reached 109.0 compared to December 2020. The annual change in the Consumer Price Index in June 2022 is 7.4%, a year ago this change was 1.6%. The monthly change of the consumer price index in June 2022, compared to May 2022, is -0.1%. (www.instat.gov.al).

The annual price increase in June was mainly influenced by the "Food and non-alcoholic beverages" group with +4.38 percentage points, followed by the "Transport" group with +1.53 percentage points. Prices of the group "Rent, water, fuel and energy" with +0.54 percentage points. The prices of the "Furniture, home appliances and home maintenance" group increased by

+0.28 percentage points. The prices of the "Hotels, cafes and restaurants" group contributed with +0.25 percentage points. The prices of the "Alcoholic beverages and tobacco" group increased by +0.23 percentage points.

The prices of the "Clothing and shoes" group increased by +0.07 percentage points. Prices of the group "Various goods and services" with +0.05 percentage points. The prices of the group "Communication" and "Educational service" with +0.02 percentage points each. Prices of the "Health" group with +0.01 percentage points. (Institute of Statistics info@instat.gov.al, www.instat.gov.al).

The conflict between Russia and Ukraine will affect the global economy through three main channels: financial sanctions, commodity prices and supply chain disruptions. (<https://www.eiu.com/n/economist-intelligence>).

The consumer faced an immediate increase in prices for all products while the wage level remained unchanged. As a developing country, the level of wages is not very high and the level of unemployment has been increasing. This immediate increase in prices had an immediate impact on the reduction of purchasing power. The consumer significantly reduced consumption for all goods. The decrease in consumption was very significant and for the basic products of the basket such as: flour, sugar, rice, pasta, eggs, milk, dairy products, as well as in the fruit and vegetable sector, there was a large decrease in consumption.

The situation of purchases and consumption of basic basket products before the price increase

To assess the impact of the Russia-Ukraine war on the impact it has had on the consumption of goods, mainly the basic basket of goods: flour, sugar, rice, oil,

etc., 122 random consumers were surveyed. To evaluate the responses of consumers, regression analysis was used to see the impact of income on the consumption of the basic products of the basket.

Regression analysis is a parametric analysis which examines the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, it shows the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Table 1

Family income impact

Modello	R	R-quadrato	R-quadrato corretto	Deviazione standard Errore della stima	Variazione dell'adattamento					Durbin-Watson
					Variazione di R-quadrato	Variazione di F	df1	df2	Sig. Variazione di F	
1	.735 ^a	.055	.047	.51057	.055	7.032	1	120	.0901	1.977

a. Predittori: (Costante), family income

b. Variabile dipendente : the consumption of the basic products of the basket before the price increase

Table 2

Statistiche descrittive

	Media	Deviazione standard Variabile	N
the consumption of the basic products of the basket before the price increase	1.3934	.52314	122
family income	54663.9344	18406.16617	122

Table 3

Correlazioni

	the consumption of the basic products of the basket before the price increase	family income
Correlazione di Pearson	1.000	.235
	.235	1.000
Sig. (1 coda)	.	.005
	.005	.
N	122	122

From the model, we notice that 73.5% is explained by the coefficient of determination, which shows that 73.5% of the consumption of basic products in the basket before the price increase is explained by the level of family income, while the rest is explained by the remaining factors.

The correlation coefficient = 0.901 shows the strength of the connection between the variables included in the model. The closer this coefficient is to 1,

the stronger the relationship between the variables. In this case the connection is strong and positive.

Hypothesis

H0: Family income has no influence on the purchase of basic basket products.

H1: Family income has an impact on the purchase of basic basket products.

Table 4

Anova^a: The Consumption of the Basic Products of the Basket Before the Price Increase

Modello	Somma dei quadrati	df	Media dei quadrati	F	Sig.
1 Regressione	1.833	1	1.833	7.032	.009 ^b
Residuo	31.282	120	.261		
Totale	33.115	121			

a. Variabile dipendente: the consumption of the basic products of the basket before the price increase

b. Predittori: (Costante), family income

As can be seen in the regression analysis table above, according to the level of security, the hypothesis: H1, according to which family responsibilities have an impact on the amount of purchases of basic basket products and their consumption, remains true.

Table 5

Coefficients^a: Family income impact

Modello	Coefficients non standardizzati		Coefficients standardizzati	t	Sig.	Intervallo di confidenza 95.0% per B	
	B	Deviazione standard Errore	Beta			Limite inferiore	Limite superiore
(Costante)	1.028	.145		7.070	.000	.740	1.316
family income	6.687	.000	.735	2.652	.009	.000	.000

a. Variabile dipendente: the consumption of the basic products of the basket before the price increase

b. Costante: family income

Model: Consumption of basic products in the basket before the price increase = 1.028 + 6.687* family income + e

From the above linear factorial model, it is observed that family income has a positive impact on the purchase and consumption of basic basket products such as sugar, flour, rice, milk, bread, water, oil. With the increase in income, the consumer will increase the demand for these necessary products according to his needs, the number of family members, their use, etc.

The situation of purchases and consumption of basic basket products after the price increase

The unforeseen inflation that faced our country, but not only, directly affected the decline in purchasing power. Consumers, for the same amount of income they received before inflation, now in the conditions of inflation manage to buy less goods, even an immediate reduction was observed for the purchase of basic basket products.

Table 6

Riepilogo del modello^b : Total costs of basic products in the basket products before the price increase

Modello	R	R-quadrato	R-quadrato corretto	Deviazione standard Errore della stima	Variazione dell'adattamento					Durbin-Watson
					Variazione di R-quadrato	Variazione di F	df1	df2	Sig. Variazione di F	
1	.707 ^a	.500	.496	4257.18410	.500	120.009	1	120	.000	1.764

a. Predittori: (Costante), family income b. Variabile dipendente: Total costs of basic products in the basket products before the price increase

From the model, we notice that 70.7% is explained by the coefficient of determination, which shows that 70.7% of the total costs of the basic products in the basket before the price increase is explained by the level of family income, while the rest is explained by the remaining factors.

The correlation coefficient = 0.500 shows the strength of the connection between the variables included in the model. The closer this coefficient is to 1, the stronger the relationship between the variables. In this case the connection is almost strong and positive.

Table 7

Coefficients^a: Total cost for the base product of the basket before the price increase

Modello	Coefficients non standardizzati		Coefficients standardizzati	t	Sig.	Intervallo di confidenza 95.0% per B	
	B	Deviazione standard Errore	Beta			Limite inferiore	Limite superiore
(Costante)	6834.810	1212.292		5.638	.000	4434.557	9235.063
family income	.230	.021	.707	10.955	.000	.189	.272

a. Variabile dipendente: total cost for the base product of the basket before the price increase

Model: 6834.810 + 0.230* family income + e .
So the total costs of products depend positively on the level of income that consumers have.

Hypothesis:

H0: Family income does not affect the total expenses for the purchase of products.

H1: Family income affects the total expenses for the purchase of products

Table 8

Anova^a: Total cost for the base product of the basket before the price increase

Modello	Somma dei quadrati	df	Media dei quadrati	F	Sig.
1	2175002086.025	1	2175002086.025	120.009	.000 ^b
Residuo	2174833979.548	120	18123616.496		
Totale	4349836065.574	121			

a. Variabile dipendente: total cost for the base product of the basket before the price increase

b. Predittori: (Costante), family income

From the variation analysis table, it can be seen that the hypothesis H1 is true, so the income has a weight in the total costs of the consumer for the purchase of the basic products of the basket. Also, the weight of family income in the total expenses made by the consumer for the purchase of basic products in the conditions of inflation has been evaluated.

Table 9

Riepilogo del modello^b: Total cost for the base product of the basket with the price increase

Modello	R	R-quadrato	R-quadrato corretto	Deviazione standard Errore della stima	Variazione dell'adattamento					Durbin-Watson
					Variazione di R-quadrato	Variazione di F	df1	df2	Sig. Variazione di F	
1	.193 ^a	.637	.029	31592.78142	.637	4.625	1	120	.034	2.068

a. Predittori: (Costante), family income

b. Variabile dipendente total cost for the base product of the basket with the price increase.

From the model we notice that 19.3% is explained by the coefficient of determination which shows that 19.3% of the total costs of the basic products of the basket after the price increase is explained by the level of family income while the rest is explained by the remaining factors e.

The correlation coefficient = 0.637 shows the strength of the connection between the variables included in the model. The closer this coefficient is to 1,

the stronger the relationship between the variables. In this case the connection is strong and positive.

Hypothesis:

H0: Family income has no influence on the purchase costs of high – priced products.

H1: Family income has influence on the purchase costs of high – priced products.

Table 10

Anova^a: Total cost per product based on the basket with increased prices

Modello	Somma dei quadrati	df	Media dei quadrati	F	Sig.
1	4615744388.873	1	4615744388.873	4.625	.034 ^b
Residuo	119772460529.160	120	998103837.743		
Totale	124388204918.033	121			

a. Variabile dipendente: total cost per product based on the basket with increased prices

b. Predittori: (Costante family income)

From the variation analysis table, it can be seen that the hypothesis H1 is true, so the income has a weight in the total costs of the consumer for the purchase of the basic products of the basket.

Table 11

Coefficienti^a: Total cost per product based on the basket with increased prices

Modello	Coefficienti non standardizzati		Coefficienti standardizzati	t	Sig.	Intervallo di confidenza 95.0% per B	
	B	Deviazione standard Errore				Beta	Limite inferiore
(Costante)	2206.376	8996.478		.245	.807	-15606.024	20018.776
family income	.336	.156	.193	2.150	.034	.027	.645

a. Variabile dipendente: total cost per product based on the basket with increased prices

Model: $2206.376 + 0.336 \cdot \text{family income} + e$.

Income has a positive impact on the determination of expenses for goods and services.

During the period of inflation that our country is going through, it was noticed, among others, the reduction in the consumption of basic products, but not only; the rate at which one good can be exchanged for another changes and the overall purchasing power of our income changes. These reflect a change in demand as a result of the price change, orienting the consumer towards the effect of replacing one good with another, but on the other hand, the increase in price has caused the purchasing power of our money to decrease, which seriously affects the decline of the demand for goods caused by the income effect.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

This study aimed to study the effect of inflation on the demand for the basic goods of the basket such as flour, sugar, rice, oil, etc. to see if the consumption of these goods has changed with the increase in prices or not. The study proved the best that inflation affected the reduction of the well-being of consumers; decrease in demand in the market, decrease in purchasing power in the market. So inflation had a negative impact on the well-being of consumers. The hypotheses verified during this study showed the importance of the consumer's income in the consumption and purchase of basic basket products. In inflation conditions, consumers buy less due to the decrease in the purchasing power of the consumer's income, causing a change in demand. The consumer tends to replace a product with another one

that has a lower selling price. Inflation negatively affected not only consumer welfare but the entire economy as a whole.

Recommendations

Based on the negative impact that inflation has on the economy as a whole and specifically on the well-being of consumers, as the object of this study we recommend:

Significant indexation of salaries for each category.

Subsidizing the electricity bills of families who have a very low level of income.

Increased control over product prices in the market to curb abuses of their increase.

Keeping inflation under control through appropriate monetary policies.

The intervention of the government and through certain policies that affect tax reliefs for producers or various subsidies so that the price for the consumer is as affordable as possible.

References

1. GAP INSTITUTE 2022
2. <https://www.eiu.com/n/economist>
3. Institute of Statistics info@instat.gov.al, www.instat.gov.al.
4. Russia's War in Ukraine: Consequences for European Countries' Businesses and Economies Anatolij Prohorovs.
5. <https://www.eiu.com/n/economist/intelligence>
6. Author's study.